

Supplementary File 2. ChatGPT-4 generated pathway evaluation framework.

Rate each pathway as it relates to pancreatic cancer in the following categories from 1-5.

Pathway Relevance (Weight: High):

- Assess the significance of the signaling pathway in the context of the disease of interest (e.g., pancreatic cancer).
- Assign a score based on the known involvement of the pathway in disease initiation, progression, or resistance.

Target Druggability (Weight: High):

- Evaluate the availability of druggable targets within the pathway, such as specific kinases, receptors, or downstream effectors.
- Assign a score based on the presence of well-characterized drug targets and the availability of approved or investigational drugs.

Genetic Alterations (Weight: Moderate):

- Consider the frequency and relevance of genetic alterations within the pathway in the target population.
- Assign a score based on the prevalence of pathway mutations or amplifications in the disease.

Biomarker Availability (Weight: Moderate):

- Assess the availability of reliable biomarkers associated with the pathway's activity.
- Assign a score based on the feasibility of using biomarkers for patient stratification and monitoring treatment response.

Evidence from Literature (Weight: Moderate):

- Review the existing literature for studies supporting the efficacy of targeting the pathway in the disease.
- Assign a score based on the strength and consistency of evidence from preclinical and clinical studies.

Safety Profile (Weight: Moderate):

- Evaluate the safety profile of drugs targeting the pathway, considering potential side effects and off-target effects.

- Assign a score based on the known safety and tolerability of drugs associated with the pathway.

Scoring System:

- Assign numerical scores (e.g., 1 to 5) for each criterion, with higher scores indicating better suitability.
- Multiply the score for each criterion by its assigned weight.
 - High - 5
 - Moderate -3
 - Low - 1
- Sum the weighted scores to obtain a total score for each signaling pathway.
- The pathway with the highest total score is considered the most likely candidate for drug targeting.

Supplementary File 3. Cohorts included in Kaplan Meier Plotter used for survival analysis.

12 GEO and 4 ICGC datasets used by Kaplan Meier Plotter [29]. In our study, we only used samples that included tumor stage information (473 samples) for survival analyses.

Dataset	Project title	Platform	Genes (n)	Samples (n)
GSE84219	Expression analysis in ductal adenocarcinoma in patients with low and high survival after tumor resection	GPL14951	19,252	30
GSE78229	Microarray gene-expression profiles of 50 pancreatic tumors tissue from patients with pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma	GPL6244	19,988	50
GSE179351	Radiation therapy enhances immunotherapy response in microsatellite-stable colorectal and pancreatic adenocarcinoma in a phase II trial	GPL18573	20,210	12
GSE172356	Tumor microbiome contributes to an aggressive phenotype in the basal-like subtype of pancreatic cancer	GPL20795	19,240+	53
GSE57495	Microarray analysis of 63 patients with pancreatic cancer tissues resulted in the identification of a 15-gene signature to predict overall survival	GPL15048	19,874	63
GSE79668	RNA-sequencing of human pancreatic adenocarcinoma cancer tissues	GPL11154	19,175	51
GSE85916	Patients with human resected pancreatic cancer	GPL13667	19,322	80
GSE28735	Microarray gene-expression profiles of 45 matching pairs of pancreatic tumor and adjacent non-tumor tissues from 45 patients with pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma	GPL6244	17,546	90
GSE124230	Pancreatic cancer prognosis is predicted by chromatin accessibility	GPL11154	19,745	49
GSE102238	Gene expression signatures associated with perineural invasion in pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma	GPL19072	8735	100
GSE62452	Microarray gene-expression profiles of 69 pancreatic tumors and 61 adjacent non-tumor tissue	GPL6244	19,988	130

	from patients with pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma			
GSE71729	Virtual microdissection of pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma reveals tumor and stroma subtypes	GPL20769	18,229	252
PACA-AU	Pancreatic cancer – ductal Adenocarcinoma – Australia	GPL10558 & Illumina Hi seq	20,082+	269
PACA-CA	Pancreatic cancer – Ductal adenocarcinoma – Canada	GPL10558	19,757+	234
PAAD-US	Pancreatic cancer – Adenocarcinoma – United States	Illumina Hi seq	19,689	145
PAEN-AU	Pancreatic cancer – Endocrine neoplasms – Australia	GPL10558 & Illumina Hi seq	20,058+	32

Supplementary File 4. Current FDA-approved small molecule drugs targeting SRC.

Drug	Target Disease/Function	Status	Clinical Trials
Dasatinib	chronic myeloid leukemia	approved, investigational	phase 4
Bosutinib	chronic myelogenous leukemia	approved	phase 4
Nintedanib	idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, systemic sclerosis-associated interstitial lung disease, non-small cell lung cancer	approved	phase 4
Ponatinib	chronic myeloid leukemia	approved, investigational	phase 3
Fostamatinib	chronic immune thrombocytopenia	approved, investigational	phase 3
Tirbanibulin	actinic keratosis on face/scalp	approved, investigational	phase 4